

Methods of correction of navigation systems and navigation complexes

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Abstract

The article considers methods of correction of navigation systems (NS) and navigation complexes (NC) on the basis of information received by aircraft control devices (AIR). It is taken into account that the NC includes gyroscopic systems, various radar stations (radars), other navigation and orientation systems, as well as GPS or GLONASS. Errors of autonomous navigation systems, algorithmic methods of compensation of errors of navigation systems and complexes are considered. The inertial navigation system (INS), which is the basic system of the NC, is considered separately, and its errors are divided into methodical and instrumental. Cases are taken into account when it is impossible to correct the NC aircraft due to the temporary absence of a signal from an external source of information. Satellite emergency signals are subject to active and passive interference. The methods of using autonomous INS correction algorithms taking into account the algorithms of estimation, control, complexation and forecasting are investigated.

Key words: autonomous navigation system, error, estimation algorithm, complexing, self-organization algorithm, genetic algorithm.

Introduction

Successful solution of aircraft management tasks is mostly determined by the level of development of measuring equipment. Information signals of measuring systems have errors due to design features and operating conditions of the aircraft. Improving the accuracy of measurement information involves the study of errors and their subsequent algorithmic compensation (Ageyev V. M., Pavlova N. V., 1990; Kuzovkov N. T., Salychev O. S., 1982; Neusypin K. A., 2009). The issue of improving the accuracy of emergencies operating in different modes is considered,

taking into account that the NC is the primary source of errors in the management of aircraft. In this regard, the definition and further correction of errors of the NC on the basis of the use of these methods is an urgent task of the article.

The purpose of this article is to analyze the methods of error correction in NS and NC to solve the selected problem, taking into account the methods of metrological support, methods of decision theory, methods of analysis and synthesis of complex systems.

Results and discussion

Presentation of the main research material

The errors of autonomous NS include methodical and instrumental, given that the basic system of NC is INS.

Methodical errors of INS are caused by

methods of carrying out measurements. Thus, these include errors caused, for example, inaccurate knowledge of the structure and parameters of the Earth's gravitational field and quantitative characteristics of its shape, as well

as errors due to the simplification of computational algorithms. Usually the main part of methodological errors is successfully compensated.

Instrumental errors of INS, Instrumental errors of INS, arising from errors of inertial sensors and computing device – random drift of gyroscopes, instability of scale factors of torque sensors of gyroscopes and accelerometers, errors of information transmission, etc. The cause of other errors are design and technological factors, which are considered separately.

Examining the response of autonomous INS to certain perturbing factors, we can clarify the nature of INS errors. In this case, the zero signal is a signal that, for whatever reason, appears at the output of the accelerometer, although at that time there is no acceleration. This signal is usually small, is an oscillation with the Schuler period according to (Ageyev V. M., Pavlova N. V., 1990) and can lead to significant errors according to (Kuzovkov N. T., Salychev O. S., 1982).

If the error of the accelerometer varies in proportion to the time of its operation, the error of the INS can be represented as an increasing component over time and superimposed on it a sinusoidal component.

The INS error in determining the distance traveled due to the errors of the first integrator is a sinusoidal oscillation according to (Kuzovkov

N. T., Salychev O. S., 1982).

The dominant influence on the total error of the INS in determining the distance traveled has the drift speed of gyroscopes. The systematic drift rate of gyroscopes causes a subsequently increasing component of the INS error, as well as the oscillating component of the Schuler period according to (Ageyev V. M., Pavlova N. V., 1990; Kuzovkov N. T., Salychev O. S., 1982). The drift rate increasing over time leads to an INS error, which can be represented as two components. The first varies in proportion to the square of the time of operation of the INS, and the second fluctuates according to the Schuler period.

The INS error due to the inaccuracy of the gyro-stabilized platform (GSP) exhibition relative to the horizon plane is a sine wave oscillation.

The total INS error in determining the location of the aircraft of the above factors increases over time.

Taking into account the above, the equations of INS errors are considered. It is assumed that the reference coordinate system should be realized by means of GSP, and in fact, due to errors, the axes of the accelerometers are oriented along other axes according to (Kuzovkov N. T., Salychev O. S., 1982; Neusypin K. A., 2009). In this regard, in the discrete form, the equations of INS errors in the form of a system of equations are as follows:

$$\begin{cases} x_k = \varphi_{x_{k-1} + \omega_{k-1}}; \\ x_k = [\delta V_{xk} \delta V_{yk} \alpha_k \beta_k \Psi_k \varepsilon_{xk} \varepsilon_{yk} \varepsilon_{zk}]^T; \\ w_{k-1} = [B_x B_y 0 0 0 w_{x_{k-1}} w_{y_{k-1}} w_{z_{k-1}}]^T; \end{cases}$$

which can be written in matrix form:

$$\Phi = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & -gT & f_y T & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & gT & 0 & -f_x T & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\frac{T}{R} & 1 & 0 & 0 & T & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{T}{R} & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & T & 0 \\ \frac{T}{R} \operatorname{tg} \varphi & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & T \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 - \mu T & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 - \mu T & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 - \mu T \end{bmatrix}, (1)$$

Where δV_{xk} , δV_{yk} – INS velocity determination errors; α , β , ψ – the angles of deviation of the GSP relative to the reference coordinate system; ε_x , ε_y , ε_z – GSP drift velocities; ϕ – location latitude; R – the radius of the earth; g – gravity acceleration; f_x , f_y – horizontal accelerations of the object on which the INS is installed; μ – the average frequency of random drift changes; T – sampling period; B_x , B_y – offset zeros of the accelerometers; w_x , w_y , w_z – perturbing external influences. Neglecting cross-links, you can write the INS error equation separately for each information channel.

Instrumental errors are divided into errors of accelerometers, integrators, gyroscopes and inaccuracy of GSP exhibition according to (Kuzovkov N. T., Salychev O. S., 1982; Neusypin K. A., 2009).

With a sufficiently long time of operation of the INS, the errors can reach unacceptably large values. Therefore, it is necessary to adjust the INS using different sources of external navigation information, or to compensate for errors using the internal connections of the system.

Methods of correction of navigation information. Correction of navigation information is carried out in autonomous and corrective modes with the help of additional signals. Algorithms for compensating the errors of autonomous INS due to the internal connections of the system are developed in detail according to (Kuzovkov N. T., Salychev O. S., 1982; Neusypin K. A., 2009). The measurement vector in such algorithms is formed on the basis of signals coming from the sensors of precession angles. Inertial navigation systems equipped with similar algorithms have residual errors caused by various perturbing factors, commensurate with the errors caused by the dynamic drift of the GSP. Thus, in the autonomous operation of the INS throughout the flight interval of the aircraft, the methods of correction of the INS using only internal information are used.

The most complete compensation of INS errors is carried out by means of algorithmic processing of the information in INS with the additional sensor of navigation information

external to INS. Compensation for errors in the source information of the system is usually carried out by estimation algorithms, for example, using a Kalman filter, which theoretically allows to obtain an optimal estimate of the INS state vector. In practice, direct adaptive modifications of the Kalman filter are used, which allow to obtain non-divergent estimates of INS errors in accordance with (Kuzovkov N. T., Salychev O. S., 1982; Neusypin K. A., 2009; Ivakhnenko A.G., Myuller Y. YA., 1985).

Correction of INS from external sources of information with the use of different algorithms can significantly reduce the errors of navigation information. The INS with an external source of information, as which the GPS or GLONASS system is used, is considered. In this case, the input signal for the estimation algorithm is, for example, the difference between the speed measurements using INS and GPS or GLONASS. INS errors make up the state vector of the system and include errors in the speed, angle and drift of gyroscopes, and GPS or GLONASS errors are measurement noise.

Using the estimation algorithm, an estimate of the state vector is obtained, i.e. an estimate of all observed INS errors. Next, the estimation of INS errors is algebraically subtracted from the original INS signal, which contains reliable information about the speed and location of the aircraft and INS errors. Thus, the output signal compensates for INS errors in determining the navigation parameters.

Estimation of INS errors can be used in the controller to compensate for errors in speed, angle and drift of gyroscopes in the structure of the INS, thereby reducing the amplitude of error oscillations and improving the quality of the transient process.

The use of estimation algorithms to increase the accuracy of the measuring complex of the aircraft allows to make a correction in the output information signal without interfering with the dynamics of the measuring systems.

There are cases when it is impossible to correct the NC aircraft due to the temporary absence of a signal from an external source of information. Signals of satellite navigation

systems are sensitive to active and passive interference. Therefore, there may be intervals of flight of the aircraft, when it is impossible to obtain reliable navigational information.

In the absence of signals from the GPS or GLONASS system, other sensors are used to correct the INS, such as an angular velocity sensor according to (Neusypin K. A., 2009).

A large number of different systems and sensors of navigation information allows for complex information processing. Joint processing of information from multiple sensors or systems is called complexation. The set of algorithmically related NS and sensors is called NC.

NC is a set of systems and sensors, based on the principle of operation of which are based on various physical laws. These systems are combined algorithmically.

The most common scheme of NC is the INS, adopted as the basic system, several sensors of external information, as well as algorithms for integration and evaluation. Complexation algorithms are signal processing algorithms that come from the emergency and additional sensors used according to (Ageyev V. M., Pavlova N. V., 1990; Neusypin K. A., 2009). Increasing the number of measuring systems theoretically allows to obtain information about the navigation parameters of the object with great accuracy. When using systems with different accuracy characteristics and, due to the imperfection of the algorithmic software, the accuracy of determining the navigation information is reduced. Therefore, with the help of complexing algorithms, systems are selected that allow to obtain the most reliable information on the navigation parameters of the aircraft, or in the process of joint signal processing from different systems, the most reliable information is selected according to (Neusypin K. A., 2009).

The accuracy of the corrected INS largely depends on the errors of the external source of information and the errors of the algorithm used, in particular on the adequacy of the mathematical model of INS errors.

With long-term operation of the INS without correction, the angles of deviation of the GSP increase, resulting in the inadequacy of the

mathematical model to the real process of changing the errors of the INS. Then apply the correction of INS in the structure of the system using control algorithms according to (Neusypin K. A., 2009; Ivakhnenko A.G., Myuller Y.YA., 1985).

Errors in the structure of the INS, as a rule, are compensated by adaptive regulators according to (Ageyev V. M., Pavlova N. V., 1990; Neusypin K. A., 2009). The disadvantage of this approach is the high sensitivity of the circuit to errors in determining the INS.

If the sources of external information are disabled, then the correction of the emergency is carried out using forecasting algorithms. In this case, you need to use some predictive model or form a model on board the aircraft in flight. Using the model, the navigation system errors are predicted, then the predicted error estimates are used in the known correction schemes according to (Kuzovkov N. T., Salychev O. S., 1982; Neusypin K. A., 2009; Stepanov O. A., 1998).

To increase the accuracy of the INS operation in the autonomous mode, a mathematical model of the INS errors in the previous correcting mode was built. The task of forecasting errors and using it in the source information to compensate for errors is solved using algorithms on board the aircraft. By using state-of-the-art precision systems, time and material costs can be reduced. The implementation of algorithms on board the aircraft in the onboard digital computer system (ODCS) imposes specific requirements on them, the main of which is the small amount of machine memory allocated for the implementation of algorithms.

Predictive models are used in the correction schemes of the navigation system in the disappearance of signals from external measuring systems. In the short-term disappearance of the output signals of INS, GPS or GLONASS and other systems, a priori models are usually used to predict the useful signal. A priori models, such as type (1), can be used for INS. In the conditions of long absence of signals from external meters a priori models over time become inadequate to real process of change of errors of INS in real time. Therefore, models of INS errors must be formed during the operation

of the aircraft. Known methods of building models differ in the accuracy and amount of machine memory required for implementation in ODCS. The simplest methods are various modifications of linear trends according to (Neusypin K. A., 2009; Ivakhnenko A.G., Myuller Y.YA., 1985). More sophisticated methods allow you to build high-precision models, but require more time and a significant amount of machine memory ODCS. Such methods include various neural networks (NN), algorithms of self – organization (AS) and genetic algorithms (GA).

NN allow to form models of researched objects with rather high accuracy, but demand at the same time long time for realization of process of training.

The method of self-organization can be used in the conditions of the minimum volume of a priori information, and also without consideration of some essential factors. This method can be used in conditions of exceeding (several times) the interference of the useful signal.

The possibility of forecasting without taking into account some determining factors is explained by the fact that in complex systems the factors are correlated with each other. Therefore, the measurement of one factor contains information about other factors associated with the measured factor.

The work of GA is an iterative process that lasts until a certain number of generations of selection or any other stop criterion is realized.

Each generation of GA undergoes selection, crossover, and mutation.

Using only GA to solve the problem is inefficient, as the search for the optimal value of the parameters of the approximating function is not purposeful enough. Finding the global minimum, in the general case, is quite difficult due to the presence of a significant number of local extremes and such a task requires large computational costs with almost complete search of possible solutions with a certain accuracy.

To reduce computational costs when building a forecasting model in the ODCS aircraft can be selected GA with redundancy of successful models. This modified GA is an algorithm with a high sampling coefficient. Reserved models take part in crossover, which is organized similarly to meiosis according to (Rutkovskaya D., Pilin'skiy M., Rutkovskiy L., 2006; Rotshteyn A.P., 1999). Meiosis involves the implementation of a method of reducing the number of chromosomes during division, i.e. crossing individuals with a reduction in the number of chromosomes. Such a modification allows you to synthesize a compact GA, which almost does not lose in the accuracy of model construction, and wins in speed.

Thus, the most popular classical methods of constructing INS error models are listed. Taking into account the peculiarities of the implementation of algorithms in ODCS, it is advisable to give preference to self-organization algorithms and modified compact GA.

Conclusions

1. Conceptual algorithmic methods of increasing the accuracy of navigation information are considered.

2. It is established that for correction of autonomous INS it is expedient to use algorithms of compensation of errors by means of the information received from the sensor of angular speed.

3. In the corrected mode, the compensation of INS errors is carried out in the output signal of the system using adaptive estimation algorithms.

4. When using several sensors of navigation information in the aircraft, it is necessary to

select the measurement information using the algorithms of complexation.

5. Compensation of INS errors in the offline mode on the basis of the information received in the previous corrected mode, is carried out in an output signal by means of predictive models. A priori models and linear trends are used in the short-term forecast. For long-term forecast, the models are built on board the aircraft. It is recommended to obtain predictive models implemented in BCOM using self-organization algorithms and modified compact GAs.

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